

Tracing impact events in clay samples with iridium anomaly at and above the Cretaceous/Paleogene boundary at Byala, Eastern Bulgaria

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Abstract. Elemental composition of two groups of 12 clay samples, at and above the Cretaceous/Paleogene (K/Pg) boundary at Byala (Black Sea shore, Eastern Bulgaria), is studied by Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) in order to trace impact events. Iridium anomaly and a certain set of trace elements, together with biostratigraphic data, point to two possible impact events recorded: the first one (at the K/Pg boundary), linked to the giant Chicxulub impact in Mexico; and a second one (above the K/Pg boundary), possibly linked to the later in age, smaller and closer in distance, Boltysh impact in Ukraine.

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INTRODUCTION

Impact events, caused by the fall of large cosmic bodies on Earth and leaving traces in the form of geochemical and isotope anomalies, are among the most interesting interdisciplinary subjects of study of modern geoscience. The Cretaceous/Paleogene (K/Pg; also known as K/T or Cretaceous/Tertiary) boundary mass extinction is considered one of the five major mass extinctions. It occurred about 66 million years ago and is associated with an Ir anom-

aly (Alvarez *et al.*, 1979, 1980, 1982). This K/Pg phenomenon is widely considered a consequence of the impact of a large celestial body that caused the Chicxulub crater (astrobleme) on the Yucatan Peninsula in Mexico (see Gurov and Gozhik, 2006; Schulte *et al.*, 2010; Goderis *et al.*, 2021; in some views, the impact predates the K/Pg boundary: Keller *et al.*, 2004). Part of this extinction includes dinosaurs, as well as many mollusks, including ammonites and belemnites. Mesozoic ecosystems underwent a dramatic turnover, which in the early

Paleocene (Danian) led to the evolution of new species that filled vacated ecological niches. Worldwide, the K/Pg boundary clay is linked to a single impact phenomenon (or several such phenomena) and corresponding extinction events, known as the K/Pg mass extinction.

Geochemical studies using samples from different countries around the world show that the iridium content in K/Pg boundary strata is very high. Elements of the platinum group (PGE), due to their low mobility in sedimentary rocks, serve as good geochemical markers for stratigraphic studies (Hull *et al.*, 2011; Savel'eva and Savel'ev, 2016). The iridium anomaly, which was originally found in the Gubbio section, Italy, allowed the development of the impact hypothesis (Alvarez *et al.*, 1979, 1980, 1982). Other criteria for identifying impact phenomena are geochemical signatures for chondritic of near-chondritic element ratios, Ni-rich spinels, shocked quartz, microspherules of different compositions, PGE phases, metallic phases and alloys and even microtektites and impact diamonds (*e.g.*, Rampino, 1982; Bohor *et al.*, 1987; Grachev, 2009). The relationship between abnormal concentrations of iridium and other platinoids, as well as cosmogenic elements such as Cr, Co and Ni, at some stratigraphic levels with mass extinction of organisms and the geological events that cause them is still much debated. In such profiles, the average iridium content in the Earth's crust is usually exceeded by 2–3 orders of magnitude. Other points of view explain the elevated content of iridium, together with increased concentrations of uranium, vanadium, molybdenum, nickel, phosphorus and other elements, as indicators of active volcanism (Bhandari *et al.*, 1994; Font *et al.*, 2016, 2018; Gavrillov *et al.*, 2019). It is also possible that both the extraterrestrial and volcanogenic scenarios work together (Keller *et al.*, 2018).

The study of samples of boundary deposits for ^{244}Pu content, as an indicator of supernova explosion, indicated a negative result (Alvarez *et al.*, 1979, 1980; Orth *et al.*, 1988). The reduced $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios in samples from the Caravaca boundary impact layer in Spain are linked to cosmic and mantle material (DePaolo *et al.*, 1983) and similar data are suggested for the $^{187}\text{Os}/^{186}\text{Os}$ ratio in samples from the boundary layer in New Zealand (Lichte *et al.*, 1986).

Several sites with Ir anomaly and related geochemical and mineralogical evidence at the K/Pg boundary have been reported from the territory of Bulgaria to date: 1) in marine hemipelagic sediments near the town of Byala, Varna District – 6.1

ppb Ir (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993a, b; review in Sinnyovskiy, 2003); 2) in shallow-marine sediments near Moravitsa at the Kamenitsa River, Vratsa District – 7–11 ppb Ir (Sinnyovskiy, 1998, 2003; Kostov and Tzankarska, 2000); 3) Kozya Reka, 15 km east of the “Wonderful Rocks” geological site, Varna District – 5 ppb Ir (Vangelov and Sinnyovskiy, 2000; Sinnyovskiy, 2003, 2013); and 4) Kreta, Pleven District – 3–5 ppb Ir (Sultanov, 2009).

The most informative and best studied among them, from an interdisciplinary point of view, are the geological sections in the vicinity of the town of Byala (Fig. 1) along the Black Sea coast (Stoykova and Ivanov, 1992, 2004; Preisinger *et al.*, 1993a, b; 2002; Ivanov and Stoykova, 1994; Rögl *et al.*, 1996; Kostov and Tzankarska, 1997; Belivanova, 1998; Ilieva, 2000; Stoykova *et al.*, 2000; Adatte *et al.*, 2002; Peybernès *et al.*, 2004; Stoykova and Ivanov, 2004; Kostov *et al.*, 2013; Stoykova, 2022).

Fig. 1. Location of the studied sections around Byala, Eastern Bulgaria (*a*, *b*). Position of sections B2b and B2b' at Byala (modified after Stoykova, 2022) as example of sites for clay sample groups 1 and 2 (*c*).

The iridium and trace elements were determined by INAA. Mineralogical and geochemical analyses of the corresponding sections, below and above the K/Pg boundary, revealed fluctuations in carbonate content, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, Ir and some REE (Adate *et al.*, 2002). The short-term fallout at the K/Pg boundary at section Byala 2b is characterized by shocked quartz grains and anomalies of Ir, Cr and other siderophile elements, as well as K-T spinels (Ni-rich magnesioferrites with variable Cr contents and etched pits), as well as a 5–10 cm layer with evidence for reworking of fallout with Ir, Cr, and K-T spinels (Preisinger *et al.*, 2002).

The geochemical analysis of the K/Pg boundary sections in the vicinity of Byala is important for further comparison with the data obtained from similar sites worldwide. The results obtained during the present study allow conclusions whether this is the only fall of a single celestial body on Earth (destruction by one body), or it may be a fall of several asteroids/celestial bodies that have fallen also before and/or after the K/Pg boundary event.

MATERIAL

Twelve clay samples were chosen for this study from sections B1–B3 (Fig. 1a–c) at and above the K/Pg boundary (for correspondent mineralogical

content, see Kostov and Tzankarska, 1997; Kostov *et al.*, 2013). Their position in the respective sections is indicated in Table 1.

According to their stratigraphic position, geochemical data and paleontological content, the studied clay samples are described in two groups: 1) samples 3–11 from the K/Pg boundary clay bed, linked to the Chicxulub impact in Mexico; and 2) samples 1, 2 and 12, from the black clay bed ~6.30 m above the K/Pg boundary, possibly linked in source to the Boltysh impact in Ukraine, which occurred ~500,000 years after the K/Pg impact and correspond in age to the early Paleocene.

GEOCHEMICAL AND MINERALOGICAL SETTING

Initial geochemical studies, by semi-quantitative spectral analysis of 18 samples of clay-layer sections from the area of the town of Byala (sections B1, B2b, B2c and B3; at section B2b additional clay samples B2b' were collected at ~6.30 m in the Paleocene deposits), were carried out in 1996 as part of an NSF funded project at the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. A total number of 26 main and trace elements have been identified (Li, Be, B, Al, P, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ga, Sr, Y, Zr, Mo, Ag, Sn, Ba, Ce, Pb and

Table 1
Samples and groups (1 and 2) for the studied clay samples from sections 1–3 at Byala

Sample N	Section	Thickness (mm)	Lithological and mineralogical characteristic	Group
1	B1-1	5 mm	black clay, middle part of clay layer (quartz; calcite; illite; smectite; albite); 1.2 km north of Cape Sveti Atanas at the sea shore	2
2	B1-2	5 mm	grey clay, below B1-1	2
3	B2b-3	10 mm	black clay, middle part of clay layer (calcite; quartz; sericite; smectite; feldspars – albite and orthoclase); 2.7 km north of Cape Sveti Atanas at the sea shore	1
4	B2b-4	10 mm	pale grey clay, below B2b-3 (calcite; quartz; sericite; smectite)	1
5	B2b-5	10 mm	black clay from second near-by site	1
6	B2b-6	10 mm	grey clay, below B2b-5 from second site	1
7	B2b-7	10 mm	grey clay, below B2b-8 from third site	1
8	B2b-8	10 mm	black clay, middle part of clay from third site	1
9	B2b-9	20 mm	grey clay, above B2b-8 from third site	1
10	B2c-10	4 mm	black to brown clay, middle part of clay layer (quartz; calcite; albite; sericite; illite); 3.3 km north of Cape Sveti Atanas at the sea shore	1
11	B3-11	7 mm	black to brown clay from middle part of clay layer (quartz; calcite; illite; sericite; smectite); 4.3 km north of Cape Sveti Atanas at the sea shore	1
12	B2b'-12	2 mm	plastic lower part of black clay, ~6.30 m above the K/Pg boundary at section B2b (calcite; quartz; sericite)	2

Th). At the same time, the mineral composition of these samples was determined (Kostov and Tzankanska, 1997) and an attempt to correlate iridium with some of the possible cosmogenic chemical elements was made. It has been assumed that there is a direct correlation between the concentrations of siderophile elements (Cr, Co and Ni with possible impact origin character) and most of the chalcophile elements (Cu, Zn, Ga, Mo, Sn, Pb) mainly in dark grey to black or grey-green middle parts of the clay layers. Elements such as B, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Co, Ni, Cu, Ga and Ce, as well as Pb and Th, were found with increased concentrations in the dark to black seams of the clay layers. Elevated contents of P and Mn were noted in the upper carbonate-bearing parts of the clay layer, as well as in the B2b' samples (in the last case with identified apatite phase). The Zr content is higher in brown seams above the black ones. No particular enrichment in a specific element was observed in any of the studied sections, situated in a distance of about 3 km in a south–north direction along the beach at Byala, Black Sea coast of Bulgaria.

In an NAA study of a sequence of eight samples from the B2b boundary clay bed, 19 chemical elements were tested and published (similar results were reported for samples from the Byala 2c section, with one of the samples – N 8), corresponding to the black boundary layer with maximum content of Ir 6.1 ppb, which correlated with high contents of Cr, Co and Ni (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993b). In 2013, geochemical results were published for 13 samples from the same B1–B3 sections at Byala according to data from ICP-OES (Kostov *et al.*, 2013). More accurate data for 14 chemical elements (Li, B, Na, Mg, Al, K, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ba) are already presented. In the B2b' sample, a maximum concentration in the content of Cr, Ni, Co and Zn is noted.

The non-calcite residue of the clay samples consists of a silica (quartz) and feldspar phase as registered by X-ray diffraction. In the >0.063 fraction dominate transparent silica, irregular or rounded (spherical or oval shaped), grains, as well as silica pseudomorphs on foraminifer shells of different morphology (spherical, cylindrical, spindle-shaped or complex; in cases with hollow central part or with some sort of mineral phase; Belivanova, 1998; Stoykova *et al.*, 2000). Possible iron sulphide phases, as well as tiny black, grey or reddish (hematite-bearing) phases, are observed in the <0.01 mm fraction.

Ni-rich magnesioferrite spinels with variable Cr contents are reported from the B2b section as

formed in the mesosphere of the Earth after the K/Pg impact (Aslanian *et al.*, 1996; Preisinger *et al.*, 2002). The size of the octahedra is between 1 μm and 20 μm , and the average size is 6 μm . The spinel concentration peak corresponds to the maximum of the Ir content found by INAA. It could, therefore, be assumed that about half of the Ir is contained in the K-T spinels. Such K-T spinels have etched pits, whereas polarity reversal spinels from other stratigraphic levels in the section have none, as H_2SO_4 aerosols existed in the stratosphere only after the K-T event. More than half of the investigated crystals of sizes greater than 5 μm have surfaces with etched pits on the (111) face, rarely on the (100) face. The investigated K-Pg spinels from Byala 2b are similar to the Ir-bearing K-Pg spinels from the section in Caravaca, Spain (Bohor *et al.*, 1986; Smit *et al.*, 2004; Robin and Rocchia, 1998, for El Kef, Tunisia, and Grachev *et al.*, 2007, for Gams, Austria). Magnesioferrite spinel, in cases with elongated depressions, is considered to be fairly common in the basal 2 cm of the boundary marl at Zumaia with 350 spinel grains per square centimeter (Doehe and Margolis, 1990).

In the present study, data about 40 chemical elements for 12 clay samples are obtained by NAA: Na, Mg, Al, K, Ca, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Zn, As, Se, Rb, Sr, Zr, Mo, Ag, Sb, Sc, Ba, La, Ce, Nd, Sm, Eu, Tb, Dy, Ho, Yb, Hf, Ta, W, Ir, Au, Th and U (Tables 2–4). The first five elements, as well as iron, are associated with the composition of the main mineral phases contained in different parts of the clay layer – mainly quartz with silicates and calcite (Kostov and Tzankanska, 1997; Stoykova *et al.*, 2000).

EXPERIMENTAL INSTRUMENTATION AND METHOD

In the present study, the NAA method was chosen to achieve the necessary high accuracy, especially in the determination of trace concentrations of certain elements of interest. The elementary composition of the clay samples was studied at the Laboratory of Neutron Physics of the Joint Institute for Nuclear Research in Dubna, Russian Federation. The neutrons for the NAA investigations were delivered from the IBR-2M fast pulsed reactor, one of the best modern facilities for high-flux neutron irradiation. With an average heat power of 2 MW, the peak pulse power reaches 1500 MW. The average density of the thermal neutron flux at the moderator surface is 10^{13} neutrons $\text{cm}^2 \times \text{s}^{-1}$, and its pulse den-

Table 2

Content of major and trace elements in clay samples from the sections around Byala (in ppm; *Ir and Au – in ppb; na – not available): 1 – sample 3 black; 2 – sample 4 grey; 3 – sample 5 black; 4 – sample 6 grey; 5 – sample 7 grey; 6 – sample 8 black; 7 – sample 9 grey; 8 – sample 10 brown; 9 – sample 11 brown; 10 – error, %

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Na	5800	3950	4600	4200	4140	5800	5700	3680	4800	6.7
Mg	33000	15500	38000	29800	20100	37000	14800	25600	22500	9.5
Al	65700	32600	80000	69400	38300	71000	28800	52100	48300	3.8
K	25500	12500	32000	19800	12900	24200	22500	16200	18400	9
Ca	58000	184000	10100	116000	193000	62000	300000	185000	114000	10.6
Sc	16.4	9.25	18.7	13.4	8.36	16.6	16.1	9.36	10.9	2.8
Ti	3350	1660	4780	3810	2300	3840	1480	3000	2630	6.3
V	127	66.4	152	139	78	139	61.8	100	95	4.2
Cr	159	112	266	172	111	161	137	116	182	4.6
Mn	194	393	106	237	309	200	750	500	253	6.9
Fe	39000	23600	48000	34200	29500	37600	36300	26300	32300	5.8
Co	24.4	24.7	72	52	29.2	20.4	20.2	23.3	10.5	6.8
Ni	177	107	570	500	87	120	119	148	79	8.3
Zn	140	92	355	199	85	104	120	153	94	4.5
As	na	na	39	10.4	24.9	12.4	na	na	na	3
Se	1.6	3.35	10.4	5.1	0.8	4.9	4.5	0.85	<0.6	18.5
Rb	155	78	220	117	76	143	139	94	116	16.3
Sr	1040	980	890	630	1450	3830	3910	630	404	6.8
Zr	102	75	120	85	70	111	100	76	80	7.6
Mo	0.69	0.43	1.3	0.55	0.74	1.4	1.3	0.76	0.48	30.8
Sb	1.29	2.25	2.44	0.98	0.91	1.31	1.21	0.93	0.86	5.3
Cs	12.1	5	16.7	7.34	4.19	10.9	10.2	6.65	6.37	3.3
Ba	220	156	270	209	172	280	290	240	280	13.9
La	15.4	16.4	13.8	16.6	14.7	17.6	17.6	16.1	17	4
Ce	29.4	29.1	25	29.3	25.5	31.4	31.4	30.4	31.2	6.8
Nd	na	na	23	na	na	25	16	15.8	na	19.4
Sm	2.85	2.97	2.42	3.2	2.65	3.4	3.3	3.2	3.1	9.6
Eu	na	10.8								
Tb	0.359	0.385	0.314	0.415	0.352	0.421	0.404	0.373	0.391	3.6
Dy	2.1	na	na	na	na	2	2.4	2	1.7	25.5
Ho	<0.162	<0.144	<0.154	<0.153	<0.143	<0.193	0.61	<0.145	<0.165	27.6
Yb	1.62	1.17	1.17	1.53	1.26	1.64	1.47	1.29	1.25	15.6
Hf	3.14	1.79	3.62	2.63	1.8	3.25	3.21	2.06	2.84	5.2
Ta	0.727	0.421	0.827	0.665	0.462	0.771	0.719	0.488	0.655	3.7
W	2.3	1	2.9	2	1.2	2.3	2.1	1.2	1.5	30.5
Ir*	4.4	<1.36	<2.08	5.1	<1.37	<1.82	<1.84	<1.37	<1.37	12.6
Au*	9.6	6.9	16	14	8.9	8.7	8.3	7.2	7.3	30.6
Th	10.2	5.94	10.5	9.2	6.15	10.6	10.5	7.07	8.4	3.5
U	2.01	1.43	2.6	2.12	1.59	2.17	2.11	1.77	2.18	5.9

sity 10^{16} neutrons $\text{cm}^2 \times \text{s}^{-1}$. Four channels of the reactor, allowing irradiation by thermal and fast neutrons and by resonance (epithermal) neutrons, are allocated for research activities. The channel used in the present experiment is equipped with a cylinder-shaped 0.7-mm thick cadmium shield. More

detailed description of the IBR-2M fast pulsed reactor can be found in Shvetsov (2017).

The NAA studies were performed at the REGATA facility. The latter is connected with the IBR-2M irradiation channel through a ~50–60 m long pneumatic transport system with a delivery time of

Table 3

Comparison of geochemical data according to NAA data for clay samples with maximum Ir content from section B2b (in ppm; Fe in %; Ir in ppb): 1 – sample 3 of this study; 2 – sample 6 of this study; 3 – after Preisinger et al., 1993b; 4 – bulk decalcified sample (Preisinger et al., 2002); 5 – high Ir-bearing clay KTG7 at Gams, Austria (Egger et al., 2009); 6 – electromagnetic fraction in clay from Mangishlak, Kazakhstan (Nazarov et al., 1983)

N	1	2	3	4	5	6
Sc	16.4	13.2	20.3	15.1	12.7	1.4
Cr	159	172	269	159	136	–
Fe	3.9	3.4	4.9	4.0	3.8	48.8
Co	24.4	52.0	21.2	32.6	57.2	17.8
Ni	177	500	93	242	79	–
Rb	155	117	395	–	87	–
Sr	102	85	149	637	143	–
Sb	1.3	1.0	2.0	–	1.4	0.5
Cs	12.1	7.3	16.3	–	5.3	–
Ba	220	209	910	–	148	–
Ce	29.4	29.3	21.3	–	39.1	20.1
Tb	0.3	0.4	0.2	–	0.5	0.5
Yb	1.6	1.5	2.8	–	1.5	1.8
Hf	3.1	2.3	5.8	–	2.8	–
Ta	0.7	0.7	0.8	–	0.8	–
Ir*	4.4	5.1	6.1	5.5	6.0	4.0
Th	10.2	9.2	9.4	8.7	9.1	0.1
U	2.01	2.12	–	–	1.21	–

3–20 s. Transport containers of polyethylene and aluminum were used to bring samples to the irradiation position and back. Detailed description of the REGATA facility and the NAA methodology applied have been already published (Frontasieva, 2011).

Paper bags were used for initial storage and transportation of the materials. At the laboratory, the samples were dried to constant weight and two subsamples of about 0.1 g were prepared and packed in polyethylene foil bags for short-term irradiation and in aluminum cups for long-term irradiation. After the unloading of the transport containers, the samples were repacked and measurements of γ -ray spectra were performed. The REGATA facility is equipped with HPGe gamma-spectrometers with a resolution of 1.9 keV for the ^{60}Co 1332.4-keV γ line and a 30% relative efficiency.

To determine the concentrations of elements with short-lived radionuclides (Al, Ca, Dy, Ti, V, Mg, and Mn), irradiation time of 1 min was chosen. The cadmium-screened Channel 1 was used to activate elements characterized by long-lived

isotopes (As, Au, Ba, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Eu, Fe, Hf, Ho, Ir, K, La, Mo, Na, Nd, Ni, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sm, Sr, Ta, Tb, Th, W, Yb, Zn, Zr, U) at a neutron flux of 1.8×10^{11} neutrons $\text{cm}^2 \times \text{s}^{-1}$ and irradiation time of four days. The gamma spectra of induced activity were obtained using a Canberra HPGe detector with a resolution of 1.96 keV at 1332 keV ^{60}Co total-absorption peak. Measurement time was 15 min in the case of short-term irradiation. Following long-term irradiation, all subsamples were measured after 4 and 20 days of decay. Spectra processing was performed using the Genie2000 (Canberra) software with peak fitting verification in interactive mode. The elemental concentrations were calculated using the Concentration software developed at the Frank Laboratory of Neutron Physics, Joint Institute for Nuclear Research (Pavlov *et al.*, 2016). Quality control was ensured by simultaneous irradiation of the samples with the following certified reference materials: NIST SRM 1633c Coal fly ash, USGS AGV2 Andesite, NIST SRM 2709 Trace elements in soil, NCRM GBW07292 Platinoids, NIST 1633b Constituent Elements in Coal Fly Ash, NIST 2710

Table 4

Content of major and trace elements in studied clay beds in the Byala sections (1–5) and comparison with Yarmouk, Jordan, site (6) and the Boltysh crater (7, 8) (in ppm; *Ir and Au – in ppb; na – not available); 1 – Byala, black clay B1-1; 2 – Byala, grey clay B1-2; 3 – Byala, black clay B2b*; 4 – Byala, average data for three black clay samples from section B2b; 5 – error in % for data in columns 1–4; 6 – Yarmouk, Jordan, sample A6/C (Abboud, 2016); 7 – Boltysh crater, granite fragment BO-3A (Cernok, 2009); 8 – Boltysh crater, average data from six microcrystalline rocks identical in chemical element to glassy matrix rocks, devitrified glassy matrix rock and melt rocks (Grieve et al., 1987)

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Na	6400	3780	7600	4690	6.7	na	na	na
Mg	34000	21300	24400	36000	9.6	na	na	na
Al	73600	42200	52700	72230	3.8	na	na	na
K	30500	11900	19200	27230	9	na	na	na
Ca	23300	199000	106000	43370	10.7	na	na	na
Sc	18.7	8.99	12.5	17.2	2.8	7	8.93	na
Ti	3750	1900	2750	3990	6.4	na	na	na
V	163	491	116	139	4.1	833	95	35
Cr	146	109	167	195	4.4	2782	81.8	52
Mn	142	620	391	167	6.9	2590	na	na
Fe	41000	23300	34600	41530	5.8	na	na	na
Co	22	12.1	51	38.9	6.8	41	14.4	20
Ni	84	46	196	289	8.3	650	31	40
Zn	144	76	144	200	4.6	425	110	54
As	na	na	na	25.7	-	8	<0.9	na
Se	1.98	1.23	8.9	5.6	6.4	8	<1.3	na
Rb	173	83	122	173	16.3	87	223	183
Sr	470	730	790	1920	6.8	2292	217	209
Zr	131	58	117	111	6.5	122	299	178
Mo	0.66	0.3	0.48	1.13	31.4	606	na	na
Sb	1.85	0.61	1.29	1.68	5.2	2	<0.1	na
Cs	11	5.05	9.2	13.2	3.3	na	2.88	na
Ba	250	173	250	257	13.9	1068	806	712
La	21.9	20.1	19.8	15.6	4	na	35.2	na
Ce	36.6	32.6	35.2	28.6	6.7	na	72.3	na
Nd	na	na	na	24	-	na	28.7	na
Sm	4	3.4	3.3	2.89	9.6	na	5.36	na
Eu	0.88	0.88	0.95	na	10.8	na	1.27	na
Tb	0.481	0.455	0.44	0.365	3.6	na	0.59	na
Dy	na	2	2.2	2.1	25.9	na	na	na
Ho	<0.415	<0.147	<0.187	<0.157	-	na	na	na
Yb	2	1.49	1.52	1.48	15.5	na	0.94	na
Hf	3.56	1.78	2.71	3.34	5.2	na	7.22	na
Ta	0.92	0.45	0.671	0.775	3.6	na	1.51	na
W	2	1.1	1.7	2.5	30.5	na	<3.0	na
Ir*	<5.93	<4.34	<5.15	2.77	-	2.1	<1.2	na
Au*	12	7.1	11	11.4	30.4	6	<1.6	na
Th	13	6.7	8.9	10.4	3.5	na	13.6	na
U	3.19	1.61	1.98	2.29	5.9	na	2.8	na
Ir/Au	0.49	0.61	0.47	0.24	-	0.35	0.75	na

Montana Soil, and BCR 667 Estuarine sediment (trace elements). A good agreement between the experimentally obtained and certified values was achieved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Clay samples at the K/Pg boundary (Sample Group 1)

Geochemical data for clay bed samples in sections B2b, B2c and B3, corresponding to the K/Pg boundary interval, are shown in Table 2. The distribution of most elements in samples from section B2b is in good agreement with previous data from the same section (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993b), as well as with the similar clay layer from the Gams locality in Austria (Table 3).

Maximum Ir contents of 4–6 ppb, apparently correlated with Au (0.010–0.016 ppm), were observed in samples from sections B1 and B2b (also including B2b'). These data correspond, more or less, to the already published data for Ir in the same sections (Kostov and Tzankarska, 2000). The mean value of the Ir/Au ratio in seven of the clay samples with the highest respective Ir contents is 0.38 (ranging 0.13–0.61). Probably half of the Ir content is considered to be linked to Ni-containing spinel (magnesioferrite), found in the B2b K/Pg clay layer (Aslanian *et al.*, 1996; Preisinger *et al.*, 2002).

The presence of a second, smaller peak of Ir at ~7 cm above the K/Pg boundary in section B2b, along with Cr, is interpreted as a result of reworking (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993a, b), as well as related to a possible second impact event (Stoykova *et al.*, 2000). Clay layers with PGE anomalies at Byala 2b suggest multiple events. Clay layer 1 marks the K/Pg boundary and contains an Ir anomaly of 6.1 ppb, whereas clay layer 2, about 5–8 cm above, contains a small Ir anomaly of 0.22 ppb together with a major Pd anomaly (1.34 ppb). It is linked also to anomalies in Ru (0.30 ppb) and Rh (0.13 ppb) that may suggest a volcanic source (Adatte *et al.*, 2002). Biostratigraphically, it falls in the lower Danian *P. eugubina* Zone (planktonic foraminifera) and the NP1 *Biantholithus sparsus* nannofossil Zone. Similar second peak, situated at 5–10 cm above the main geochemical anomaly, with enrichment of Co and some other elements, has been recorded in Gams, Austria, where three Ir anomalies have been detected – one before and two after the K/Pg boundary, in which Ir is found with elevated values of V, Cr, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As and Pb (Grachov *et al.*, 2005;

Grachov, 2009). The Ir content of the boundary clay bed at section B3 is 2.3 ppb (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993b; Adatte *et al.*, 2002).

Based on various analyses of clay layers around the world, it is assumed that iridium correlates with other platinumoid group elements, with Ni, Co, Au, As, Cu, Zn, as well as with Cr and Ti (Aleksseev *et al.*, 1990; cf. Brooks *et al.*, 1986; Hansen *et al.*, 1987; Strong *et al.*, 1987; Rocchia *et al.*, 1990; Smit *et al.*, 2004; Hull *et al.*, 2011; Racki *et al.*, 2011; Premović *et al.*, 2012; Esmeray-Senleta *et al.*, 2017; Premović and Ilić, 2018). In some other K/Pg sites, for example in Denmark, there is a vertical displacement of 6 mm of the concentration of Ir and Cr at the contact, and Co, Zn, As, Sb and Au – above the contact (Hansen *et al.*, 1988). Impact spherules are usually concentrated in the middle part of the clay layer at the K/Pg boundary in Italy, which correlate with the Ir anomaly, and shock quartz occurs only in the lower parts of the clay layer with a displacement of about 4 mm (Montanari, 1991).

High contents of elements such as Cr, Ni and Co, along with Zn, were recorded in samples from sections B2b, B2c and B3 (Table 2). Arsenic was noted only in some samples from section B2b, and Sr was determined to have highest concentrations in all B2b samples. Manganese has elevated values not in the black seams, but in the gray seams of clay layers from sections B1 and B2b, probably linked to higher carbonate content. Sample 5 from section B2b contains the highest concentration of about 15 of the studied elements, including Fe, Rb, Sb, and Cs. Silver (0.93 ppm, error 18.3%) was detected only in sample 11 from section B3. With respect to lithophile elements, Ir is correlated with Al and Ta, and among REE, Ce is associated with Sm below and above the boundary layer (Michel *et al.*, 1985).

Of the REE, Nd was found only in black seam samples from section B2b, as well as in a sample from section B2c, and Eu – only in samples from sections B1 and B2b'. Both B1 and B2b' samples are characterized by elevated values of La, Ce, Sm, Eu and Tb, Ho and Yb. Th and U values are higher in the black seam samples from sections B1 and B2b. Elevated uranium contents, together with Cr and Ti, have been recorded for Al-containing samples from the iridium zone of the boundary clay layer in an ocean drilling sample (Michel *et al.*, 1983). Among other similar K/Pg worldwide sites, U is found in increased amounts in Danish clays, genetically linked to diagenesis processes (Kunzendorf *et al.*, 1990).

The new geochemical data obtained from sections B1, B2b, B2c and B3 at Byala (Tables 2–3) turned out to be similar or close to the previous data for the studied elements by NAA (Preisinger *et al.*, 1993b), semi-quantitative spectral analysis (unpublished, cf. Stoykova *et al.*, 2000) and data from ICP-OES (Kostov *et al.*, 2013). Maximum values of most of the studied elements are reported in the dark-colored to black seams of the boundary clay bed in all sections. The positive correlation of elevated content of Cr, Ni and Co and Ir concentration is confirmed. Other elements with high values of concentration in dark seam clay samples are Sc, Ti, V, Fe, Zn, Rb, Sr, Zr, Mo, Sb, Cs, Ba, Au, Th and U.

Clay samples above the K/Pg boundary (Sample Group 2)

In the B1 samples and the B2b' sample from above the K/Pg boundary, high Ir values of 4–6 ppb, as well as not so significant contents of Cr, Co and Ni can be noted in comparison with black clay seams from sections B2b and B2c (Table 4). These samples show highest values of some REEs such as La, Ce, Sm, Eu and Tb (also Yb for sample 1). Sample 1 (B1-1) displays also highest content of Sc, V, Zr, Ta, Th and U, compared to all other studied samples (Tables 2–3). This draws attention to a possible next impact phenomenon, after the main K/Pg event, in the early Paleocene (Danian). Higher content of Be (1–3 ppm), Ti ($\geq 1\%$), Mn (600–1000 ppm), and Ba (100–300 ppm) is also recorded in B2b' black clay samples and in some B1 clay samples (R.I. Kostov, semi-quantitative spectral analysis, unpublished). Samples from the B2b' level do not demonstrate any relation with an increased content of chalcophile elements, which points to another source of material.

The Boltysh impact structure (astrobleme), 24 km in diameter, is located in central Ukraine (48°45' N; 32°10' E; Schmidt, 1997; Gurov and Gozhik, 2005, 2006; Gurov *et al.*, 2006; 2011; Cernok, 2009; Pickersgill *et al.*, 2017). Its $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age was previously estimated to be 65.17 ± 0.64 Ma (Kelley and Gurov, 2002; Jolley *et al.*, 2010; Pickersgill *et al.*, 2017), which is within uncertainty of the age of the Chicxulub impact structure at 66.038 ± 0.49 Ma and the K/Pg boundary at 66.043 ± 0.043 Ma (Renne *et al.*, 2013). A recommendation has been made for applying $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating with precision better than $\pm 2\%$ for a 65.82 ± 0.64 Ma (Jourdan *et al.*, 2012). New $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age data for the Boltysh astrobleme was recently published by Pickersgill *et*

al. (2021) – $65.39 \pm 0.14/0.16$ Ma. It shows that the impact occurred ~ 0.65 Ma after the mass extinction (Pickersgill *et al.*, 2021). The Boltysh bedrocks are Precambrian granites and granite gneisses making up the crystalline basement of the Ukrainian Shield and the impact structure is overlain by >500 m of younger sedimentary rocks (Grieve *et al.*, 1987; Gurov and Gozhik, 2005, 2006, 2015; Gurov *et al.*, 2006; McDonald *et al.*, 2009). Carbon isotope and palynological analysis of the fine-grained organic carbon-rich lacustrine sediments that filled the Boltysh impact crater preserve a uniquely complete and detailed geological record. A negative carbon isotope excursion, as well as fossil ostracods, have been evidenced (Dykan and Dykan, 2020) in an expanded section of the early Danian that lasted as long as ~ 340 ky (Gilmour *et al.*, 2013). The Boltysh impact crater is situated at about 750 km to the NE of the sections at Byala, where the studied clay beds come from.

In the black clay sample 12 from section B2b', the agglutinated foraminifera *Glomospira charoides*, *Glomospira regularis* and *Ammodiscus* spp. were observed. They have well-preserved hyaline type shells, which are white opaque, with spiral elements. Such preservation of benthic foraminifer shells has been found in samples from the K/Pg boundary clay both at Byala and Mezdra (Moravitsa) sites in Bulgaria. The mineral content is attributed predominantly to a feldspar composition. Foraminifera's cores of a transparent glass-like type have been observed and attributed to the genera *Gyroidinoides*, *Anomalina*, *Oolina* and *Nodosaria*. The presence of *Globanomalina (Planorotalites) compressa* suggests an early Paleocene age (P1a(2) zone of Keller, 1988, or P1a–P1b zones of Berggren *et al.*, 1995). Species of the same age and zones are known also from the El Kef site in Tunisia above the K/Pg boundary (Keller *et al.*, 1995). *Globanomalina compressa* as a Paleogene species is recorded also at the B1 section (Peybernès *et al.*, 2004; P1c biozone after Gilabert *et al.*, 2021). Some transparent echinoid spines have been observed as well. In the Danian at Byala, only *Echinocorys sulcatus*, *E. edhemi* and *Cyclaster* cf. *danicus* are reported (Ilieva, 2000; see also scheme in Ivanov and Stoykova, 1994).

From a biostratigraphic point of view, the clay layer at ~ 6.30 m above the K/Pg boundary falls within the lower Danian, NP2 nannofossil zone, as well as P1b planktonic foraminifer zone (Stoykova *et al.*, 2005; Stoykova, 2022). As for the hyaline species, Jacobsen *et al.* (2000) found that, in the Maastrichtian–Danian chalk in the North Sea, there is up

to 60% α -quartz, represented by nm-sized spherical particles and aggregates formed directly by inorganic precipitation. The alternative idea is that they were formed initially as some form of opal, later on replaced by α -quartz.

Five discrete laminations (seams, each between 2–5 mm in thickness) of clayey shale in limestones across the K/Pg boundary at the Yarmouk River area in Jordan display anomalous content of Ir and some other elements such as V, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Se and Mo. The Ir content is as follows: at the K/T boundary, sample 16/K-T with 7.8 ppb; above at 0.90 m, A13/g with 4.5 ppb; at 1.00 m, A9/E with 5.0 ppb; at 4.6 m, A6/C with 2.1 ppb; at 8.0 m above A3/D with 1.6 ppb (Abboud, 2016). Clay laminations also contain minor amounts of Sc, Nd and Nb as account for possible extraterrestrial origins. The sample A3/D at 8 m above the K/Pg boundary is chosen as a possible analog of the second sample group, as recording an additional, later impact in the early Paleocene (Table 4; sample 6).

The trace element content (REE and Ir/Au ratio) for the studied clay samples is similar to those from the impact rocks of the Boltysch astrobleme (Table 4; samples 7, 8). The average Ir/Au ratio in three samples with highest Ir content (as well as of Ru, Rh and Pt) from the Boltysch crater is 2.24 (McDonald *et al.*, 2000).

CONCLUSION

The geochemical composition of 12 clay samples at (sections B2 and B3) and above (sections B1 and B2b') the Cretaceous/Paleogene boundary near the town of Byala, Eastern Bulgaria, is studied by NAA. Forty chemical elements are determined with varying completeness and accuracy.

Two groups of clay samples have been distinguished on geochemical and stratigraphical basis: group 1 – deposited at the time of the K/Pg boundary event (from sections B2b, B2c and B3); and group 2 – deposited at a later time, during the early Paleocene (from sections B1 and B2b'). In both cases, spatial and temporal variations of sedimentation processes may have had different influence on trace element distribution and Ir anomaly magnitude.

Specific data are obtained for clay samples from studied sections B2 and B3 regarding the distribution of Ir as an important cosmogenic benchmark for impact phenomena (globally related to the K/Pg boundary Chixulub astrobleme in Mexico, dated as

66 million years old), as well as in samples of different color from the same section. Moreover, apart from Ir, high values are documented for other elements (Sc, V, Cr, C, Ni, Zn, As, Sr, Mo, Sb, Cs, Ba, Th and U). They are registered in dark-colored to black seam samples of the clay layer in the studied sections.

A new hypothesis is proposed about the origin of the clay beds from sections B1 and B2b' influenced by a possible later impact (Boltysch astrobleme in Ukraine) with composition of similar impact-linked geochemical markers: in clay samples from section B1 (samples 1, 2), Paleocene in age, and from section B2b' at ~6.30 m above the K/Pg boundary (sample 12). According to stratigraphical and paleontological data, these clay samples, which are early Danian in age, display a high Ir content, high Ir/Au ratio, lower content of “cosmogenic” elements such as Cr, Co and Ni and particular geochemical fingerprint of higher content of rare earth elements (La, Ce, Sm, Eu, Tb, Ho and Yb). Most of the elements in the second sample group match the corresponding chemical distribution in impact rocks from the Boltysch astrobleme, Ukraine, considered here as a possible nearby source of sedimented materials.

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